

Item	Description	Sustained cost	Considered cost
Ferromagnetic core	φ30mmx100mm	€ 1,67	€ 2,00
Enamelled copper wire	27AWG 150m	€ 14,04	€ 15,00
3D printing cost		€ 13,97	€ 15,00
Dupont connectors	Not necessary	€ 0,10	€ 0,50
Hardware	Nuts and bolts		€ 1,00
Connection cables			€ 4,00
Total		€ 37,50	
		\$41,25	Exchange rate=1,10